

A Study on Happiness and Peace of Mind of Educators Working in the Basic Education Department Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract—In the modern competitive era maintaining life with peace of mind and feeling of happiness is highly difficult task for anyone because of fulfilling social desires, professional demands, personal responsibilities and individual's needs and others expectations. Everyone experiences stress and pain differentially. In the last few years Government of India (GOI) and Government of Uttar Pradesh has started paying emphasis on improving quality of basic education through initiatives like Mission PRERNA and NIPUN Bharat Mission. DIET lecturers and school teachers are an important part to meet the objectives of this mission. Keeping this in view the current study aims to explore level of happiness and peace of mind of school teachers and DIET lecturers. In this study total number of 165 school teachers and DIET lecturers of Uttar Pradesh were enrolled for data collection using four self-report questionnaires of Oxford Happiness questionnaire and Peace of Mind. The data were analyzed by using descriptive analysis and t- test through SPSS. As per the results, Mean score of happiness of school teachers were 3.26 while DIET lecturers were 2.56. The t test score (5.289, $p > 0.01$) shows significant difference between levels of happiness among school teachers and DIET Lecturers. School teachers reported experiencing higher levels of happiness than DIET lecturers. Furthermore, the mean score of peace of mind (PoM) for school teachers was 19.40, while DIET lecturers scored 18.53, indicating a difference in their experiences. However, the t-test score (0.548, $p < 0.05$) reveals no significant difference between the two groups. Despite this, school teachers generally report a greater sense of peace of mind compared to DIET lecturers. One possible reason for this could be the nature of the roles and responsibilities assigned i.e. DIET need to perform varied tasks related to administration, teaching and curriculum development.

I. INTRODUCTION

Happiness refers to a state of positive emotion when people experiencing joyful feelings, cheerful mind, and slightly increased level of psychomotor activities. Different individuals experience happiness in different ways. People find happiness in various ways: some through reading books, others by spending money, taking risks, avoiding problems, confronting challenges, or accumulating wealth. However, there is no single activity, thing, or situation that guarantees happiness for everyone. Every individual wants to experience happiness and peace of mind (feeling of calm or not being worried) in their life. Studies have depicted number of benefits of happiness; good physical health, boosting immunity, and reducing stress (Davidson, Mostofsky, & Whang, 2010; Papousek, Nauschnegg, Paechter, Lackner, Goswami, & Schuler, 2010; Steptoe & Wardle, 2011) but happiness is an individual's subjective experience. It can be vary from one person to other person and from one situation to the other. One person may experience happiness by doing an activity in a normal situation but same activity may not bring happiness in different situation or context. In different situations, the level of happiness is different from the previous experience. Happiness is a relative term. It is related to individuals feeling of satisfaction. Once the need is fulfilled, people feel satisfied and feeling satisfaction attain happiness. It is determined by many factors such as need of achievement, purpose of achievement, effort in acts, level of achievement, time of achievement, expectations and appreciations. Peace of mind is a state of mind when individuals feel relaxed, cool and calm. It often involves contentment and clarity in mind which allows individual to feel secure and balanced in their thoughts and emotions. In today's competitive world, achieving peace of mind and happiness is a challenging task for everyone. People's personal needs, social desires, professional demands, personal responsibilities, and the expectations of others contribute to high levels of stress and pain. Students also experience high level of stress, comparative feelings and trying to gain high level of achievement if their study and good job. In recent years, the Government of India and the Government of Uttar Pradesh have initiated efforts to enhance the quality of basic education through Mission PRERNA and the NIPUN Bharat Mission. These initiatives aim to help students achieve their goals with peace of mind and minimal stress. .

The present study was planned with the aim to explore level of happiness and peace of mind of two different cadres of employees of basic education (school teachers and DIET lecturers) with the **hypothesis** that there no difference between school teachers and DIET Lecturers. **Sample;** Total 165 responses were received 95 school teachers and 70 DIET lecturers through Google forms on Oxford Happiness Questionnaire and The Peace of Mind Scale (PoM).

II. Oxford Happiness Questionnaire

The Oxford Happiness Questionnaire was developed in 2002 by psychologists Michael Argyle and Peter Hills at Oxford University. This is a 29-items questionnaire, in which participants are asked to rate aspects of themselves on a 6-point Likert scale. The scale has an internal reliability value of 0.91, test-retest reliability of .73 and the concurrent validity of .73.

III. THE PEACE OF MIND SCALE (POM)

Peace of Mind Scale (Lee, Lin, Huang & Fredrickson, 2012) consists of 7 items. It is a self-report measure having a 5 point Likert scale. It has been used to find out the peace of mind (inner peace) of the individual. The 5 point scale ranges from 1 = not at all, 2 = some of the time, 3 = often, 4 = most of the time to 5 = all of the time. The scores range from 7 to 35. Higher scores indicate greater and better peace of mind. It has been standardized and validated in both the populations, including young adults (Lee, Lin, Huang & Fredrickson, 2012) and older adults (Tendhar, 2014). This scale has five positive worded statements like, 'my mind is free and at ease' and two reverse worded statements like, 'it is difficult for me to feel settled'. Studies revealed PoM to have good criterion related validity and good discriminant validity. The alpha reliability coefficient of the PoM was .91.

IV. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Data was entered in the data base computer programmer and was analyzed using the statistical package for social science. **Descriptive analysis and t-test** methods were used, to obtained results.

V. RESULTS

Table: Comparison on mean scores of Happiness and Peace of Mind between School Teachers and DIET Lecturers.

Var.	Groups	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-Score
Happiness	School teacher	3.26	.322	5.289**
	DIET Lecturer	2.56	.656	
Peace of Mind	School teacher	19.40	4.775	.548
	DIET Lecturer	18.53	7.219	
** Difference is significant at the 0.01 level				
* Difference is significant at the 0.05 level				
N = 165, df = 163				

The table shows the result of t-test descriptive statistics. The results revealed, Mean score of happiness of school teachers were 3.26 with 0.322 as the standard deviation while DIET lecturer's mean score were 2.56 with standard deviation were .656 which shows difference in mean scores. School teachers are experiencing more happy feelings than DIET lecturers. It means that DIET lecturers are experiencing lesser amount of happy feelings than School Teachers. The t-test score is 5.289 ($p > 0.01$) showing significant deference between school teachers and DIET Lecturers. The second objective to study difference in peace of mind of school teachers and diet lecturer was also evaluated through descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean score of PoM of school teachers were 19.40 with standard deviation of 4.775 while DIET lecturers mean score were 18.53 with standard deviation of 7.219 which shows difference in mean scores. School teachers are living with more peaceful mind than DIET lecturers. It means that DIET lecturers are living with lesser amount of peaceful mind than school teachers. The t test score of .548 ($p < 0.05$) shows no significant deference between school teachers and DIET Lecturers. It means that School teachers are living with more peaceful mind than DIET lecturers. DIET lecturers are living with lesser amount of peaceful mind than school teachers but the difference is not significant so it can be said that that schools teachers are also not living always with peace of mind. Sometimes they are also living with restlessness in mind and DIET lecturers are also not living always with restless mind, they are also sometimes living with peace of mind.

One possible reason for this difference could be the nature of their roles and responsibilities. School teachers often have more direct interactions with students, which can foster a sense of purpose and fulfillment. In contrast, DIET lecturers may face additional pressures related to administrative duties and curriculum development, which could contribute to their comparatively lower sense of peace.

VI. DISCUSSION

The study finding depicted that school teachers are experiencing better levels of happiness and peace of mind than DIET lecturers. It indicates that school teachers are feeling more relax, cool calm and happier than DIET lecturers. It could be because of nature of role and responsibilities are different. The school teachers work responsibilities are fixed they are performing only academic duties in a fix place and schedules and getting handsome salary of it while DIET lecturers role and responsibilities are different. They are performing academic, research, supervision, training and administrative duties as per need. On the basis of the results, the hypothesis was rejected.

VII. CONCLUSION

The findings depicted that nature of job and job profile is contributing important role in experience of happiness and peace of mind.

IMPLICATIONS:

- The study can help to understand professional differences and its effect on individual's level of happiness.
- The study can help to understand professional differences and its effect on individual's level of peace of mind.

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